

Performance of Wealth Management Firms in India and the United States Post COVID-19: A Comparative Framework

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Abstract - This research examines the performance of wealth management companies in India and the US in the Post-COVID-19 Era, highlighting market fluctuations, changes in user sentiment, expansion, and liquidity trends. Drawing on a detailed daily trading record from January 2021 to December 2025, the study comprises a total of 12 wealth management sector giants across both economies. Employing summary statistics, cross evaluation and a SWOC assessment, the research reveals that Indian firms —despite operating with a smaller asset base of approximately 0.5 trillion dollars—are projected to triple their AUM by 2028, backed by quick tech adoption, favourable demographics and supporting government policies are growing fast, but they struggle with low profits, complexed regulation and increased market ups and downs. On the other hand, US firms operate within a mature ecosystem with over \$ 50 trillion in AUM and exhibit greater stability and earnings, driven by advanced robo-advisory systems, robust institutional structures, and solid investor trust. However, they must contend with tough competition and adapt to changing regulatory requirements. By combining firm-level and country-level insights, this study builds on current knowledge of global wealth management and emphasizes the need to align expansion with long-term sustainability. The findings provide valuable guidance to policymakers, investors, and professionals in the field who seek to strengthen and enhance openness in the evolving financial landscape.

Keywords - FinTech, Wealth Management, Financial Markets, India-US Comparison.

I. INTRODUCTION

Finance involves managing money, wealth, assets, liabilities, and financial planning. It can be done on an individual level, which is also known as personal finance and financial governance. This includes managing finances at the corporate level, as well as in public institutions such as government budgeting, taxation, and financial regulations.

Technology has revolutionized the conventional way of doing things, making it faster and more accessible. This integration of finance and technology is commonly known as Fintech. It is a vast ecosystem encompassing various sub-sectors, each playing a crucial role in transforming traditional financial services with advanced technology.

Some of the major areas within Fintech are Wealth Tech (Wealth Management Technology), which focuses on improving wealth management services through the use of artificial intelligence and automation. It aims to provide personalized financial plans and strategies tailored to an individual's needs and financial capacity. After that, we have InsurTech (Insurance Technology) has made significant changes in the insurance sector by leveraging AI, big data, and automation. Accessing customer profiles and formulating policies, and ensuring fair prices are charged. It tracks real-time data and provides companies with ease in reducing fraud, collecting payouts, and also offers customers instant claim processes and settlements. PayTech (Payments Technology). A significant shift occurred in payment methods, with digital payments taking center stage through innovations such as mobile wallets and QR code payments. In India, platforms such as Paytm, PhonePe, and Google Pay have enabled users to do

contactless, seamless transactions with increased security.

RegTech (Regulatory Technology). With the integration of automation and AI-driven solutions, companies can now comply more smoothly with regulatory procedures. Performing activities such as biometrics and Know Your Customer (KYC) verification helps detect fraud and suspicious transactions. It also ensures transparency and reduces human errors, resulting in lower costs.

Lastly, LendingTech enhances the credit system by directly connecting lenders with borrowers through a peer-to-peer lending model (P2P), thereby eliminating the need for brokers or banks to be intermediaries. It provides a big relief to small businesses and underserved individuals. It makes the loan available for persons with limited credit history. LendingTech has contributed to boosting economic growth and inclusion. Advances in digital innovation are significantly transforming the financial world, positioning fintech firms to play a major role in the evolution of the wealth management sector. According to the recent study, 43% of Indian High-Net-Worth Individuals save under 20% of their income, pointing to the challenges in financial planning and the urgent requirement for innovative tech-based advisory services (Economic Times 2025).

On the other hand, India's fintech sector is experiencing rapid growth. With the rise in smartphone usage, supportive government policies, and an increasing community of young tech-savvy investors. Meanwhile, the US firms leveraging artificial intelligence and mobile apps deliver wealth solutions that are low-cost, personalized, and convenient. In 2024 alone, more than 562,000 new millionaires were created in the United States, primarily due to stock market gains and increasing usage of app-based investing (Business Insider 2025). Financial technology (Fintech) is the revolutionary element that is changing the global financial ecosystem, although India and the USA are at different levels of maturity and adoption. Meanwhile, the United States has long been at the forefront and recognized as a leader in FinTech innovation, whereas India is rapidly transforming

into a fast-growing fintech market, thanks to digital advancements and favorable regulatory initiatives.

In India, the foundation of digital banking was already introduced before the COVID pandemic. However, the pandemic created a necessity for people to turn to online banking, as they had to stay at home and avoid cash transactions. During the COVID-19 lockdowns (2020-2021), restrictions on social gatherings impacted physical banking services, underscoring the limitations of the existing financial system.

Technological innovation has helped improve the barriers to financial inclusion by introducing convenient and secure digital alternatives to physical currency. In the absence of formal banking services, Digital platforms have become a vital tool for money transfer and receiving remittances. These mobile-based payment systems help more people access financial services, also enabling government initiatives to deliver welfare schemes digitally, thereby reducing the spread of health risks associated with cash handling. At the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, 80 million Indians began using digital payments at stores for the first time, highlighting how quickly India is moving towards a digital economy. According to the 2021 financial access survey, it highlights that internet banking was the primary mode in developed economies, whereas countries like India witnessed a notable rise in mobile money usage. Digital services became increasingly important during the COVID-19 pandemic, as people required digital ways to manage their finances, which is being promoted by global governments, including India, to prioritize the development of digital infrastructure and advance technology, promoting cashless transactions. Consequently, fintech experienced rapid acceleration. "Digital technology Improving Financial inclusion in India: Post-COVID Evidence by Sinha" (2024)

The IMF working paper titled "Drivers of post covid private consumption in the US "(Dao, Jirasavetakul, & Zhou, 2024) shows that the US economy rebounded sharply after COVID-19, mainly due to a surge in private consumption, People are spending

more than they did before Covid, but it has also grown steadily with the economy, playing a big role in the recovery. One of the key reasons for the increase in consumption after COVID was the significant gains in household wealth during the COVID period. Housing wealth increased by around 50%, while stock wealth increased by 25%. This growth provided many families with a sense of financial stability, increasing their willingness to spend.

This idea is also supported by previous studies, such as Quigley and Shiller (2005), who explained that when people's assets, like houses and stocks, increase, they feel more confident and are likely to increase their spending. This pattern shows that the "wealth effect" is particularly impactful for families who own their homes.

The recovery in the US labor market bounced back strongly after the pandemic, marked by low unemployment and increasing real wages, which helps drive spending across income groups. As indicated in Figure 4 of the IMF report, this recovery is characterized by real wage and employment growth, fueling economic momentum.

Between 2020- 2021, the government implemented major stimulus, including direct cash payments and unemployment benefits, which significantly increased household incomes by 4-5% of GDP. As a result, this led to approximately \$2.1 trillion in excess savings. According to Abdelrahman and Oliveira (2023), these savings support ongoing consumption even after stimulus programs were ended. While low-income households increase at a faster rate, high-income groups account for a significant share of total spending. The Consumer Expenditure Survey 2022 highlights the continued dominance of spending by wealthier segments.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Theoretical Background

The growth of the fintech sector in India marks the most significant shift in the financial industry in recent years. Indian government policy played a crucial role in enabling fintech expansion and

promoting financial inclusion. According to (Gupta), initiatives including Aadhaar-based KYC, UPI, the PMJDY, and RBI's regulatory sandboxes have collectively created a strong foundation for a digitally inclusive financial ecosystem.

These policy frameworks have facilitated a stable foundation for fintech firms to scale their innovation and improve access to formal financial services for previously excluded segments of society. Conversely, Fintech innovation in the US has primarily followed a bottom-up approach, where the private sector has led innovation with minimal regulatory frameworks. Paypal and Splitwise serve as key examples of this model, which offers tools that strengthen transparency, enhance user control, and support seamless cross-platform functionality.(Malani) The US regulators adopted a balanced approach, supporting innovation while remaining cautious. Unlike the UK and FCA, which set up an innovation hub early (FCA,2014), the US efforts focused on turning to regtech tools to manage fintech developments (BBVA Digital Regulation unit, 2016)

Yu'E Bao became the global example that highlighted for US regulators how quickly fintech firms can grow when the early regulations are missing (Powell 2014). Overall, the fintech ecosystem shows a shift from traditional bank-based systems to tech-driven solutions, reshaping both wealth management and influencing regulatory approaches.

In 2021, the Indian fintech ecosystem had expanded significantly, reaching over 6,600 companies contributing to a market valued at approximately US\$31 billion. Between 2022 and 2030, the Indian fintech market is expected to grow at 18% CAGR, with the aim of reaching a projected value of \$1.3 trillion.

Bangalore is known as the Silicon Valley of India, with established unicorns like Paytm, BharatPe, and Acko, alongside Soonicorns such as Lendingkart and Cashfree Payments, showcasing the rapid evolution of Indian startup culture (Ravichandiran & Paramasivan, 2024).

Since 2015, the Indian fintech sector has experienced significant growth, primarily driven by startups and non-banking institutions that deliver cost-effective, innovative, and technology-driven financial solutions. With the rise of digital platforms like mobile banking apps and UPI, financial services in India have undergone drastic transformation, simplifying and making them more inclusive. As per the report 2019-2020, India recorded globally in fintech adoption with the impressive rate at 87%, overtaking China. India now has a total of 6,600 fintech startups and \$286 million in venture capital investments, showing the investors' trust in India's digital financial ecosystem.

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the fintech sector's significance in promoting financial inclusion by providing easier access to vital services for underserved segments and over 57 million small businesses. In 2021, the Indian fintech market was valued at \$31 billion and is expected to grow to \$150 billion by 2025, achieving of CAGR of 22%. The rise of unicorns like Paytm, PhonePe, Razorpay, and BhartPe underlines a major evolution, making India the top spot in the Asian fintech space. (Sinha, 2022)

According to (Arner et al. 2016), the fintech sector of the United States is categorized mainly into three distinct phases: Fintech 1.0 (1866- 1967), Fintech 2.0 (1967- 2008), and 3.0(2008 to present) The launch of the transatlantic telegraph cable marked the start of fintech 1.0 by facilitating cross-border financial connectivity (Fax Authority 2015; Moore, 2000)

During the fintech 2.0 Era, digital platforms such as Fedwire and CHIPS have transformed interbank operations. The failure of Herstatt Bank heightened regulatory challenges, resulting in the formation of the Basel Committee (BIS, 2016; Arner et al, 2016) Online banking began in the 1990s; Wells Fargo was one of who first to offer, but regulators such as David Carse (1999) raised concern that such innovation brings new technological risks.

The 2008 Global financial crisis led to fintech 3.0, as people started turning to tech companies for financial services instead of banks. In 2015, a survey by Let's Talk Payments found that Americans trust tech companies more than traditional banks. As a

result, this shift opened the door for platforms such as Betterment and Wealthfront to become successful using mobile technology and APIs (Arner et al, 2016; David Link, 2016)

Worldwide, the United States remains the leader in the number of fintech firms, access to investment capital, and deep innovation capabilities. Based on the KPMG global ranking and the fintech report by (Pollari and Ruddenklau), the United States and China dominate the volume and investments of venture capital, highlighting the maturity of their fintech ecosystem (Karaki & Alsheikh) Leading technology and innovation in the marketplace fuel the US fintech landscape, as seen by companies like Robinhood, which transformed wealth management by offering commission-free trades and simple digital interfaces. According to (Malani), the Robinhood model has reshaped brokerage services and pushed established firms to modernize their products, playing a major role in the democratization of financial markets. Its focus on financial inclusion has been crucial in attracting more young and underserved investors.

According to (Panda et al), India's assets and wealth management (AWM) industry is experiencing rapid change with over 300 WealthTech startups offering services like robo advisory, personal finance management, and these solutions are designed to meet the requirements of Indian millennials and middle-income group who hold a significant role in shaping the Financial decision-making. (Taparia (2022)) points out the demographic change in the wealth management landscape. With increasing participation from both men and women in their 30s and 40s are now more actively involved in personal finance, moving away from the traditional dominance of older male participants. As a result, the Generational shift has brought new demands for greater transparency, customization, and tech-powered solutions.

Fintech growth extends beyond wealth management, significantly impacting areas such as stock trading and retail investment platforms. Technologies such as algorithmic trading, AI-powered analytics, and robo- advisors have

enhanced and improved market efficiency, as well as increased the involvement of retail investors. (VVVDNSwamyVarre)

These technological developments contributed to faster transaction processing, improved market liquidity, and reduced the overall cost of translation. Consequently, survey data reveal a 40% rise in retail stock market participation after the adoption of Fintech, with platforms like Groww, Zerodha, and Upstox leading the way in India, alongside Robinhood and Webull doing the same in the US.

Financial performance is the prominent differentiator between Indian fintech companies from those in more established markets. According to Bhowal and Shi(2025), both Paytm and PhonePe show strong liquidity. Particular PhonePe's current ratio rose from 2.10 in 2022-2023 to 4.71 in 2023-2024; however, the firm still struggles with profitability. High operational costs and poor scalability result in negative profit margins and returns on assets noted in both firms. Despite the challenges, operational efficiency, including trade receivables and payables, show that PhonePe is better equipped than Paytm in cash flow management and timely liability settlement. This gap in performance indicates that, although Indian firms are experiencing fast-paced growth, they continue to face significant challenges in achieving profitability and operational stability compared to US firms.

Empirical research on international fintech firms provided further context. Kayani et al (2024) analyzed 191 firms from North America and Europe using Global X Fintech EFT data to inquire into the impact of variables such as liquidity, leverage, and working capital to evaluate profitability. Using panel data analysis in STATA, the researchers identified that firm-specific financial characteristics were strongly associated with profitability outcomes. These observations are particularly meaningful for Indian firms, which operate in a more volatile and intense competitive environment with relatively fewer institutional frameworks.

Collectively, these studies highlight comparative yet impactful advancements in fintech-driven wealth management in both financial markets. India stands out for rapid growth, active government inclusion measures, and the development of digital infrastructure. In contrast, the US stands out as a mature financial ecosystem, focusing on innovation and promoting financial empowerment and competitive market transformation. Together, these models serve key learning and growing standards for the global fintech ecosystem.

Research Gaps

While numerous studies have been conducted individually on the fintech wealth management domains of India and the US, there are very few comparative studies that present a comprehensive picture of both countries together. The existing literature rarely integrates country-level and firm-level analysis to cover performance in the two major Fintech markets.

Existing studies are primarily conducted using monthly, quarterly, or annual financial data. However, these time frames fail to evaluate the short-term customer behavior and market adaptation. The Fintech market of both economies is highly dynamic; thus, daily data analysis can provide a better understanding of the Fintech wealth management space.

There are very few studies that have considered both qualitative and quantitative evaluation methods for understanding the financial aspects of the Indian and US Fintech wealth management markets. This limits the holistic perspective, as the firm's strategic attributes and financial performance remain underexplored.

Scope and Objectives

Scope of the Study

The study examines the post-COVID performance, volatility, and growth dynamics of six selected wealth management firms in India and six in the United States, utilizing daily high-frequency data. It provides an in-depth examination of firm-level trading volumes and returns, illustrated through statistical tables and charts. The research also compares the

Indian and US wealth management sectors, focusing on variations in firm scale, liquidity patterns, volatility, and investor trends. A SWOC (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, challenges) framework is used to assess both the market, examining strategic positioning and recovery trends. The scope is limited to these twelve firms, enabling an in-depth and focused investigation of post-pandemic developments in global wealth management.

Research Objectives

The research study is guided by 3 primary objectives

- Growth Comparison Analysis This objective evaluates the prospective growth in the Indian wealth management sector in comparison to the US, highlighting the Indian fast-paced expansion and favorable demographic support against the US's mature, steady market.
- Post-pandemic firm evaluation The objective of this study is to examine the performance of chosen firms in India and the US after COVID-19, by analyzing daily data to assess volatility, returns, and recovery patterns.
- Comparison of Indian firms to US Ones This objective is to compare firm-level performance of wealth management companies in India and the US, showcasing India's rapid growth and volatility versus the US stable and mature market.

Data and Variables

Data

The research analyzes daily trading data from publicly listed wealth management firms in India and the United States, focusing on the post-COVID period spanning January 2021 to December 2025. The sample comprises six Indian firms and six US firms for comparative analysis. The dataset was compiled from official stock exchanges' repositories and established financial databases (Yahoo Finance, Bloomberg), ensuring uniformity and reliability. Python facilitated automation, extraction, cleaning, and visualization.

1. Daily Return Performance indicator The daily return is defined as the percentage change in a stock

price from one trading day to the next, reflecting short-term performance volatility. Formula:

$$Return_{it} = \frac{(P_{it} - P_{i(t-1)})}{P_{i(t-1)}}$$

Where: P_{it} = Closing price of firm i on day t $P_{i(t-1)}$ = Closing price of firm i on day $t - 1$

2. Log volume (Liquidity Indicator) Log volume denotes the natural logarithm of daily trading volume, applied to normalize of skewed data and evaluate investor behavior.

Where: V_{it} = Total number of shares traded for firm i on day t

III. METHODOLOGY

SWOC India and the US

The Table 1 presents a comprehensive SWOC (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges) analysis comparing the Indian and U.S. fintech wealth management sectors. It highlights that India is witnessing rapid digital transformation in retail investing, driven by increased online participation and soaring SIP contributions, while the U.S. market is already mature, led by robo-advisors managing trillions in assets and focusing on innovations such as ESG investing. Despite this growth, India continues to face challenges like low financial literacy, limited-service reach, and complex regulatory frameworks, whereas the U.S. sector contends with market saturation, stringent compliance requirements, and limited personalization. In terms of opportunities, India's young and largely rural population represents significant untapped potential, while the U.S. is seeing growing demand for retirement planning and hybrid advisory models. Both markets face distinct but evolving challenges—India grappling with regulatory hurdles and market volatility, and the U.S. with cybersecurity risks and frequent policy changes—reflecting their differing stages of fintech evolution yet shared pursuit of inclusive, technology-driven wealth management.

Indian Wealth-Management Market Leaders 360 One WAM Limited

360 One WAM Limited, based in Mumbai, originally wealth and assets management institutions, named IIFL Wealth Management Limited, since 2008, dedicatedly serving has built a strong position among India's largest

Table 1: SWOC Comparison Between Indian And Us Fintech Sectors

SWOC	India	US
Strengths	A sharp rise in the Indian retail investing landscape, with 120 million unique investors projected by 2025(Statista).SIP contributions have soared to 18,000 Cr/month Economic Times) Furthermore, digital platforms are evident, with 80% of mutual fund investments happening online (Chiratae Ventures)	As of 2024, robo advisors handle assets under management of over \$1.5 trillion (Statista), and over 65% of Americans now prefer digital wealth solutions(Mordor Intelligence). Features like ESG investing and tax loss harvesting (KPMG)
Weaknesses	India's wealth management significant literacy gap, as just 30% of the Indian population is considered financially literate (SEBI Report). Complicated and ever-changing regulations create confusion for investors. Additionally, wealth management services reach only 5% of the population, which shows that professional financial advice is always limited (Chiratae Ventures).	There are more than 120 robo advisors available; they compete hard and offer lower prices to attract users (Statista). Most of these platforms don't offer personal advice, which can feel less personal, Additionally, US government bodies like the SEC and FINRA have strict rules that they must deal with (KPMG)
Opportunities	Most Indian, around 65% of the population, live outside cities (rural areas) where they don't have access to wealth management services (Business Standard). Meanwhile, investment options like Index funds and ETFs are rising by 45% every year (Statista). The country's young individuals, with a median age of just 28, are also earning and showing interest in investing (Chiratae ventures)	With 10,000 individuals retiring daily in the US, which rise increases the need for retirement planning (Forbes). Eco-friendly and ethical investing (ESG) is also increasing by 30% in 2024 (Bloomberg). Many more people also want hybrid models that offer both robo advisors and human guidance (Mordor Intelligence)
Challenges	Wealth platforms deal with financial rules by SEBI and RBI that are tricky to follow (Chiratae Ventures). They also face tough competition from big banks and other financial firms. Meanwhile, the Indian stock market is unstable and changes quickly, which adds extra risk for investors (Statista)	The U.S stock markets often fluctuate based on global developments(Statista), at the same time, tax laws and investment rules are frequently changed (KPMG). Another concern is cybersecurity, as data breaches and fraud are becoming more common (Mordor Intelligence)

high and ultra-high net worth individuals under the leadership of its founders, Karan Bhagat and Yatin Shah. In January 2023, the company changed its name to 360 ONE WAM Limited to emphasize the firm's comprehensive 360-degree vision for

providing financial services. (360 ONE Official Site, Wikipedia). The company operates into two core business segments: Wealth Management, which includes investment advisory, financial product distribution, estate planning, lending, and equity & debt broking, and Asset Management, Offering Portfolio Management services (PMS), mutual funds, and AIFs specifically designed for institutional and

professional investors. As of March 2025, 360 ONE WAM assets under management have crossed rupees 5.81 lakh crore (US\$68 billion)in managed assets, representing over 7,500 client relationships and maintaining A1+ credit ratings from CRISIL and ICRA. The company's expansion strategy includes notable acquisitions, such as Wealth Advisers India (2018), L&T Capital Market (2020), and ET Money in 2024, as well as the upcoming B&K Securities deal (2025). In April 2025, it further announced the 3.07 billion purchase of the UBS India wealth management unit, alongside UBS taking a 5% equity stake.

Motilal Oswal Financial Services Ltd.

MOFSL is a leading Indian financial services company offering a broad range of solutions, including broking, wealth and asset management, investment banking, and private equity. Established in 1987 by Motilal Oswal and Raamdeo Agrawal, the business began as a stockbroking firm and gradually expanded into various financial areas. The Company was listed on the BSE in 1990 and later on the National Stock Exchange (NSE) in 1994. Its initial public offering in 2007, with share allotment on 5 September and official listing on both exchanges on 11 September 2007. The company's focus on research-based advice, a strong distribution network, and innovative investment products has helped it become one of India's leading financial services brands. By March 2023, MOFSL was active in more than 550 cities, with over 2,500 locations, and served more than 5.5 million clients.

Nippon Life India Asset Management Ltd

Nippon Life India Asset Management Ltd. was incorporated on 24 February 1995 and began business in June 1995 under the name Reliance Mutual Fund, formed a partnership between Reliance Capital and Nippon Life Insurance Company, Japan. In October 2019, Nippon Life took over Reliance Capital's entire stake, after which the company was renamed Nippon India Mutual Fund. The Company's IPO was conducted from October 25 to 27, 2017, and its equity shares were listed on the BSE and NSE on November 6, 2017. NAM India is a leading asset management firm in India, offering a diverse range of products, including equity, debt,

hybrid, pension funds, PMS, AIF, and offshore funds. Currently, the company manages assets worth .4.31 lakh crore, distributed across 52 equity schemes, 266 debt schemes, and 40 hybrid schemes. The company, guided by MD & CEO Mr Sundeep Sikka, is supported by the global investment expertise of its parent, Nippon Life Insurance, one of Japan's largest private life insurers with deep roots in research-based asset management.

UTI Asset Management Company Ltd

UTI Assets Management Company Ltd (UTI AMC) is among India's oldest and most trusted mutual fund institutions, with origins dating back to 1964, when the Unit Trust of India introduced the nation's first mutual fund. T.T. Krishnamachari, serving as the Union Finance Minister, played a vital role in establishing the Unit Trust of India, the country's first mutual fund. The firm was formed in 2002 as the UTI Asset Management Company Ltd, following the separation of the Unit Test of India into specified undertaking and mutual fund segments. UTI AMC offers a diverse range of investment options to retail and institutional investors, including equity, debt, hybrid, and liquid funds. UTI AMC, operating from Mumbai, serves a wide range of investors through a strong and well-established network, such as banks, financial intermediaries, and client channels. The company currently serves more than 12 million investor accounts and operates across India through its extensive branch office network and financial center network. In October 2020, UTI AMC was listed on both the NSE and BSE, marking a significant step aimed at improving visibility, strengthening brand value, and ensuring liquidity for its shareholders.

Shriram Asset Management Company Ltd

Shriram Assets Management Company Ltd, part of the Shriram Group, was established by R. Thyagarajan, AVS Raja, and T. Jayaraman. the company, incorporated on 27 July 1994 and began operations on 21 November 1994 after SEBI approval, is promoted by Shriram Credit Company Limited, part of the Shriram Group, with a strong footprint in consumer finance, broking, insurance, and financial services. With over 50 years of Shriram experience and Sanlam's global support, we serve clients with personalized wealth plans. The company

was founded in Chennai in 1974 and now operates across various financial areas, serving over 3.3 crore customers and handling assets worth 3.37 lakh crore as of March 2025. Since 11 December 1996, Shriram Finance Ltd, the holding NDFC for these businesses, has been listed on the stock exchange.

HDFC Asset Management Company Ltd.

HDFC AMC was founded in 1999 by HDFC Ltd. under the vision of its founder, Hasumkhhbai Parekh, in alliance with Standard Life Investments. The company is located in Mumbai, Maharashtra, and has established itself as India's top asset. In 2018, the company managed approximately 2.92 lakh crore in AUM, with equity contributing 51%, holding a 13.7% share of total AUM and 16.8% in active equity AUM. The IPO of HDFC AMC was conducted on 25-27 July 2018, raising 2,800 crore at 1,100 per share and debuted on the BSE and NSE on 6 August 2018, with a premium, indicating high investor confidence. HDFC AMC, with its wide distribution reach, retail-driven approach, and stable profitability, is seen as a benchmark in the Indian asset management industry.

US Wealth-Management Market Leaders

Charles Schwab Corporation

The Charles Schwab Corporation is a large American financial company founded in 1971. It is located in Westlake, Texas. The company has become well-known for making stock trading more affordable, and it also helps customers with investment advice, mutual funds, retirement planning, banking, and more. As of FY 2023, the company was handling \$8.5 trillion for its clients and had more than 34 million active investors, making it one of the biggest brokerage companies in the US. Schwab has played a major role in leveraging technology in finance, offering smart investment tools and affordable, user-friendly services, such as free trading and robo-advisors. By acquiring TD Ameritrade in 2020, Schwab has become the most powerful company in the retail trading market.

Morgan Stanley

Morgan Stanley, started in 1935, is located in New York City, is a top financial company. It primarily focuses on three key areas: assisting large

institutions with securities, Wealth Management, and Investment Management. The company offers services such as investment banking, buying and selling securities, managing investments, and providing expert financial advice to large companies, public bodies, and private individuals. In FY 2023, Morgan Stanley was managing more than — \$6.2 trillion on behalf of its clients and had 85,000 global employees. The acquisition of E-Trade in 2020 helped Morgan Stanley increase its ability to offer retail brokerage services and enhance its digital offerings. The firm continues to develop its wealth management business by leveraging technology, providing personalized advice, and expanding investment options. It is publicly traded on the NYSE (New York Stock Exchange) with the symbol MS. It is one of the world's top investment banks.

Black Rock Inc

Founded in 1988 by Larry Fink, along with Robert S. Kapito and Susan Wagner, it is now a top global asset management company. The headquarters is located in New York. The company offers a variety of services related to investment and technology, including mutual funds, ETFs, risk management platforms, and expert investment advice for both everyday investors and large institutional clients. By the fiscal year 2023, BlackRock managed more than \$ 10 trillion in assets, making it the world's top asset management firm. The firm is well-known for its iShares exchange-traded funds and its powerful risk management tool, Aladdin. It is listed on the NYSE as BLK and has a global presence in more than 100 countries, promoting eco-friendly investing, tech-driven finance, and long-term investing. BlackRock's recent strategic move to scale up its presence in the private credit space by acquiring Keros Capital, a European firm focusing on venture and growth debt opportunities.

Victory Capital Holding Inc

Victory Capital Holding Inc. is a US-based investment firm with a history dating back to 1894. The firm follows a multi-boutique model, offering investment options that include mutual funds, ETFs, separately managed accounts, retirement schemes, and institutional asset management. The company's growth, driven by both acquisitions and organic

strategies, is making it a reliable asset manager for both individual and institutional clients. In February 2018, the firm conducted its IPO, releasing 11.7 million Class A shares at a price of \$13 each. Due to the market trends, the IPO was priced lower than the expected 17–19 band. Victory Capital, headquartered in San Antonio, Texas, grows its global asset management business by focusing on clients, diverse offerings, and strategic acquisitions.

LPL Financial Holding Inc.,

LPL Financial Holding Inc. was established in 1989 through the merger of Linsco (Founded in 1968 by Robert Galuber) and Private Ledger (Established in 1973 by Todd Robinson) and has grown into the country's largest independent broker-dealer in the US, with its main office in San Diego, California and additional branches in Boston, Fort Mill and Austin, the firm provides support to approximately 29,000 financial advisors and manages \$1.5 trillion in brokerage and advisory assets as of 2023. The company launched its IPO in November 2025, offering 15.66 million shares at \$30 each and debuting on the NASDAQ Global Select Market (LPLA) on November 18, 2010. The firm provides a wide range of services, including wealth management, technology platforms, and institutional advisory solutions, as part of its offerings.

Raymond James Financial, Inc.

Raymond James Financial, Inc. was founded in 1962 by Robert A. James in St. Petersburg, Florida, under the name Robert A. James Investment. The company took its present name after merging with Raymond & Associates in 1964. It emerged as Raymond James & Associates. Today, from its headquarters at 880 Carillon Parkway in St. Petersburg, the company offers wealth management, capital markets, investment banking, and asset management. In early 2024, the firm manages about 1.24 trillion in client assets and a network of nearly 8,700 financial advisors. Raymond James, listed on the NYSE under the ticker symbol RJF since 1993, is recognized for its people-first culture, cautious growth strategy, and consistent community contributions.

This study adopts a hybrid qualitative and quantitative approach to analyze the fintech wealth management sectors of India and the United States. This study employed three core methodologies: SWOC analysis, financial performance analysis, and ratio analysis.

Methodology

- SWOC: It is used to understand current strategic positioning, opportunities, and challenges that may come in the near future.
- Country-level SWOC: It was done on country level. The fintech wealth management markets of India and the US were studied, including various factors like market size, economic parameters, and legal considerations.
- Case Studies: Conducted the top 5 market leaders in the Wealth management sector. For India, the selected firms were UTI AMC, HDFC AMC, Shriram AMC, Motilal Oswal Financial Services, and Nippon Life India Asset Management. For the US, on the other hand, the analysis included Charles Schwab Corporation, Morgan Stanley, BlackRock Inc, Victory Capital Holding and LPL Financial Holding.
- Financial performance analysis: The daily financial data for the selected companies were evaluated, and the following indicators were analyzed over a specified time period.
Average Return: Measures the stock performance for a certain time period.
Volume: Volume is used as a proxy reflecting market participation and investors' confidence in the firm's performance.
This analysis will help in understanding investor behavior, market dynamics, and the company's performance in both countries.

Results and Discussion

Trading Volume Analysis

- Trading Volume of Individual Indian Firms
- UTI and SHRF lead in daily share turnover, regularly reaching peaks of over 80 million and 60 million shares, respectively. Motilal Oswal follows with a volume surge often exceeding 20 million. In contrast, HDFC AMC and 360 ONE maintain much lower activity, typically around 10

million, and HDFC AMC frequently trades below 5 million.

- Firms like UTI and SHRF attract far more speculative and institutional interest, driving occasional spikes that are more than ten times the levels seen in lower-volume stocks, such as HDFC AMC.
- Average Log Volume Trend in India
- The log volume analysis highlights varying liquidity trends among Indian wealth management firms, with Shriram Finance leading with the highest average log volume (15.50) and low volatility, suggesting reliable institutional backing. Motilal Oswal displays the highest volume volatility, indicating a pattern of reactive trading, whereas HDFC AMC and UTI AMC show steadier, lower volumes, suggesting loyal, long-term investors. 360 ONE maintains a balanced profile, combining moderate volume levels with controlled variability, reflecting its effective return generation.

As the sector average, India’s log volume offers a consistent baseline mean(13.59, low variability) that reflects steady market involvement. Alongside firm-level observations, it highlights that wealth management sectors maintain long-term liquidity despite short-term fluctuations.

From 2021 through mid-2025, the mean logarithmic trading volume for these six Indian firms increased steadily from approximately 15.0 to around 15.5.

Figure 1: Trading Volumes of Selected Indian Firms

Table 2: Summary statistics of India log volume variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SHRFLogVol	953	15.5008	0.6144999	12.5663	18.16233
360 One LogVol	953	12.49446	1.094358	9.050172	16.62632
HDFCLogVol	953	12.79014	0.6864312	10.63294	16.17387
MOTILogVol	953	12.62145	1.37285	9.50547	17.02672
NAMLogVol	953	13.40855	0.7304496	11.1612	16.58104
UTILogVol	953	12.01932	0.8632945	9.353748	15.66614
IndiaLogVol	953	15.90965	0.5551135	13.3113	18.20315

This upward trajectory signals growing liquidity and deepening market participation in the Indian wealth-management sector over the post-pandemic period.

India vs US: Comparative Log-Volume Analysis

Table 3: Comparative Log Volume Summary between India and the US Wealth Management Sectors

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
IndiaLogVol	953	15.90965	0.5551135	13.3113	18.20315
USALogVol	954	16.73942	0.3829344	15.57849	18.97373

Analyzing log volumes across India and the US reveals notable contrasts in both the scale of markets and their liquidity patterns. The US market exhibits a higher average volume (16.74) accompanied by lower fluctuations (Standard Deviation 0.38), indicating strong liquidity and sustained investor confidence. In contrast, India averages a

comparatively lower log volume (15.91) with higher variability (Std. Dev. 0.56), reflecting a

Figure 2: Average Log Volume Trend in India

trading environment that is both dynamic and less predictable. The metrics highlight the US market’s maturity with consistent and abundant liquidity, while India displays traits of an emerging market, with growing participation and occasional spikes. In line with earlier charts and statistics, this illustrates the consistency gap and demonstrates that India’s growth is associated with more volatile trading fluctuations. - Scale Gap: US asset managers trade at a higher log-volume range (16.0-17.0) compared to Indian counterparts (15.0-15.5). -Volatility Difference: The US curve shows sharper swings, most notably a drop from near 17.0 to under 16.0 in 2022, whereas India’s trend is smoother and more gradual.

The US market’s larger size and liquidity come with greater sensitivity to market events, while India exhibits a steadier growth pattern.

Figure 3: India vs US: Average Log Volume Comparison

Investment Return Analysis

Daily Return profiles of Six Indian Firms

The table presents a daily return analysis across six Indian wealth management firms, highlighting the diverse performance and risk patterns. 360 One

excels in average return (0.12%) and moderate volatility, indicating relatively efficient performance. On the other hand, Motilal Oswal (MOTI) shows the highest volatility, highlighting its high-risk profile, while HDFC AMC shows the least volatility and near-zero returns, confirming its status as, low-risk asset. UTI AMC and SHRF feature balanced profiles with moderate returns and dynamic trading behavior, while NAM blends low volatility with significant return fluctuations, pointing to potential institutional involvement.

Table 4: Daily Return Profiles of Six Indian Firms

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
360OneReturn	953	0.0012304	0.0238885	-0.115613	0.1386489
SHRFReturn	953	0.0009247	0.0228393	-0.1219339	0.1069184
HDFCReturn	953	0.0003980	0.0188382	-0.1680770	0.1131762
MOTIReturn	953	-0.0000176	0.0527697	-1.3871410	0.1116362
NAMReturn	953	0.0006864	0.0218882	-0.1323181	0.1392224
UTIReturn	953	0.0007472	0.0234521	-0.0913488	0.1404343
IndiaTotalReturn	953	0.003969	0.0993136	-1.38535	0.4031914
IndiaAvgReturn	953	0.0006615	0.0165523	-0.2308917	0.0671986

At the sector level, overall returns (India Total Return and India Avg Return) exhibit modest average gains, systemic volatility, and occasional sharp movements. These findings enhance the earlier chart analysis by assessing firm-level stability and trail risks, giving a deeper perspective on how individual firms impact overall market trends in India’s developing wealth management industry.

Daily price movements of $\pm 5\%$ are common across these stocks. Motilal Oswal and UTI occasionally breach $\pm 10\%$ during high volatility sessions. Conversely, HDFC AMC and NAM tend to stay within a 5% range.

Motilal Oswal presents a higher day-to-day risk profile, whereas firms like HDFC AMC deliver comparatively stable performance.

Figure 4: Daily Return Profiles of Six Indian Firms

Average Daily Return in India

When averaging across all six firms, returns typically fluctuate within $\pm 2\%$. Nonetheless, collective swings of up to $\pm 4\%$ occurred during the most turbulent periods of 2022 and 2023.

Even diversified exposure to India's top wealth managers requires meaningful daily volatility, underscoring systemic market risk.

India vs US: Comparative Return Volatility

Figure 5: Average Daily Return in India

Table 5: Comparative India–US Market Returns

Variable	Ob	Mean	Std.	Min	Max
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	s		Dev.		
IndiaTotal Return	953	0.003969	0.0993136	-1.38535	0.4031914
IndiaAvgReturn	953	0.0006615	0.0165523	-0.2308917	0.0671986
USATotal Return	953	0.0035613	0.0958594	-0.3788489	0.4514910
USAAvgReturn	953	0.0005936	0.0159766	-0.0631415	0.0752485

The statistical summary of market returns from India and the US illustrates the divergence between an emerging market and a mature financial landscape. Although the Indian total market return (0.40%) is slightly higher than the (0.36%) US, it is much greater volatility and a higher risk of severe losses, highlighted by a much lower minimum return – 138.55% compared to the US –37.88%. Despite firm-level averaging, daily returns in India remain more volatile, indicating a broader systemic vulnerability to market shocks.

Conversely, the US market shows more stable performance, with an average of 0.30%, the lowest volatility, and limited variation in returns. These findings reinforce the perception of the US market as dependable and trusted by investors. As shown in the earlier charts, India represents a higher risk, higher reward scenario, while the US stands out for its reliable returns within a highly liquid market –Indian sector average returns often exceed $\pm 2\%$, with peaks near $\pm 4\%$ on the most volatile days. –US average returns remain largely inside a $(+)$ 1% band, rarely stretching beyond $(+)$ 2.5%, India's daily return swings can be almost double those in the US, highlighting the higher-risk, higher-reward nature of an emerging market.

Overall Comparative Analysis Market Scale and Maturity -The US boasts roughly 50 trillion dollars in assets under management, about 100 times India's 0.5 trillion-dollar AUM. -Around 61% of US adults invest in markets, while India's 80 million Demat accounts represent a smaller share of its population.

This disparity is mirrored in the log-volume chart: US firms consistently operate at higher levels than Indian firms, confirming greater depth and liquidity. Growth Prospectus -India's AUM is projected to triple to 1.5 trillion dollars by 2028 (200% growth), versus a 30% rise to 65 trillion dollars for the US. - India's expansion is driven by a young demographic, rising disposable incomes, higher savings rates, and financial inclusion initiatives. The US growth story centers on intergenerational wealth transfer and evolving interests like ESG investing.

The steadily rising log-volume line for India visually captures this rapid market build-out.

Risk and Volatility Profiles

-India's emerging-market status yields pronounced return volatility, daily swings of 2-4% on average, and individual stocks occasionally moving over 10%.

Figure 6: Average Return: India vs US

The mature US market exhibits lower volatility, with average daily moves confined mostly within $\pm 1\%$ and extremes under ± 2.5

This contrast highlights India's high-growth, high-risk environment versus the US's stability and depth.

IV. CONCLUSION

After the post-COVID-19 period, wealth management firms in India and the United States clearly showcase the contrast between a dynamic growth market and, evolved industry. The US market, supported by an estimated \$50 trillion in assets under management, showcases a mature ecosystem characterized by stability and minimal volatility. Daily fluctuations in returns remain confined within $+1\%$ underscoring its structural depth, mature

institutional, and efficient wealth transfer mechanisms. Wealth managers combine technology, trust, and safety, making them ideal for investors who like stable and consistent results.

India, on the other hand, is a fast-growing and changing market, currently managing around \$0.5 trillion in assets, and it's expected to triple by 2028. This growth is driven by more digital tools, wider access to finance, and tech-friendly young investors, who are boosting growth; yet, it is more volatile, with daily returns typically fluctuating between $+2\%$ and $+4\%$. Although the higher risk can be challenging for firms and investors, it also means substantial rewards for those who can navigate short-term fluctuations. More people investing in mobile platforms and government-backed digital tools make India a fast-growing market in global wealth management.

Between 2021 and 2025, both India and the US experienced good growth after the pandemic, but each followed a different path. In the US, the recovery came from rising wealth, government stimulus spending, and a strong job market. Growth stemmed from the adoption of more digital tools, effective policies, and a young population. An investor's choice depends on their comfort level with risk tolerance. US returns are stable, whereas India can deliver high growth but higher price swings.

This comparison suggests that investors should tailor their strategies to the maturity of the market, the strength of the regulations, and the level of technological readiness. The analysis emphasizes the importance for firms to balance new technologies, while also teaching investors about their options. Future studies could examine how the behavior, sustainability, and AI advisory models influence the growth and change the global wealth management industry.

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